

1 **Smart textile lighting/display system with multifunctional fibre devices for large scale smart**
2 **home and IoT applications**

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40 **Abstract:** Smart textiles consist of discrete devices fabricated from – or incorporated onto –fibres.
41 Despite the tremendous progress in smart textiles for lighting/display applications, a large scale
42 approach for a smart display system with integrated multifunctional devices in traditional textile
43 platforms has yet to be demonstrated. Here we report the realisation of a fully operational 46-inch
44 smart textile lighting/display system consisting of RGB fibrous LEDs coupled with multifunctional
45 fibre devices that are capable of wireless power transmission, touch sensing, photodetection,
46 environmental/biosignal monitoring, and energy storage. The smart textile display system exhibits full
47 freedom of form factors, including flexibility, bendability, and rollability as a vivid RGB
48 lighting/grey-level-controlled full colour display apparatus with embedded fibre devices that are
49 configured to provide external stimuli detection. Our systematic design and integration strategies are
50 transformational and provide the foundation for realising highly functional smart lighting/display
51 textiles over large area for revolutionary applications on smart homes and internet of things (IoT).

52

53 Breakthroughs in materials¹⁻⁶ and process development⁷⁻¹¹ have enabled emerging smart textiles
54 technologies based on electronics with new form factors. Unlike flexible electronics, which have
55 deposited or printed devices on a single flexible substrate, textile electronics does not have limitations
56 on substrate size, dimension of processing tool and mechanical flexibility owing to fibre-structure and
57 continuous weaving process, which encourages the freedom of form factor. The revolutionary system
58 architecture with integrated electronics into fabrics using modern textile engineering principles
59 represents an attractive pathway for realising novel functionalities in textiles¹¹⁻¹⁶.

60 Smart or electronic textiles (e-textiles) consist of versatile electronic devices incorporated onto fibre
61 substances¹⁷⁻²², which have been focused on wearables²³⁻²⁶. The recent report on textile system has
62 revealed an example of wearable **single coloured** textile display with touch sensing and biosignal
63 detection capability²⁷. However, a smart textile system over large scale beyond wearable applications
64 has yet to be demonstrated such as curtain lighting/display or digital signage. Moreover, high
65 luminance RGB colour display and various signal detection followed by a real-time illustration on a
66 standalone textile display have not been suggested. **The systematic integration of versatile fibre**
67 **devices into textile over large scale could be realized that meets harsh requirements including (i)**
68 **material/device design compatible with textile technology, (ii) non-destructive weaving pattern for**
69 **fibre device, (iii) the interconnection method applicable to textile platform, and iv) instant expression**
70 **of visual signal from F-device to F-display by signal processing/coding.**

71 Herein, to realise a broad range of multifunctionalities in a single smart textile display system, we
72 integrated one output (fibre LED) and **six input devices, which are compatible with symmetric and**
73 **asymmetric weaving pattern,** including; (i) F-radio frequency antenna (F-RF), (ii) F-photodetector,
74 (iii) F-touch sensor, (iv) F-temperature sensor, (v) F-biosensor module, and (vi) F-energy storage that
75 assembled within a natural cotton textile platform. Enhanced control over dimension/performance of
76 devices under mechanical alteration of our F-devices enabled responsive output signal expression
77 after weaving process with long-term stability (over a year). The concept of a smart textile display
78 system for smart homes and real-life IoT applications is built on the developed F-devices delivering
79 processed signals directly to the textile display to enable real-time monitoring/visualising of those

80 signals. F-LED, F-energy storage, and F-temperature were woven at one time while woven F-RF
81 antenna, F-biosensor module, F-photodetector, and F-touch sensor were integrated as Lego-like
82 manner. This Lego-like design is to suggest, (i) post-upgradability, (ii) expanding smart textile system
83 to hundred-inch wide, (iii) seamless operation of textile display with additional textile gadgets. As we
84 have realised our textile system for smart home applications, our prototype of 46-inch system is
85 expected to be much larger when used for real-life applications.

86

87 **Results**

88 **Fabrication of smart textile system by weaving process**

89 Figure 1 shows the primary steps to realise the fully operational 46-inch smart textile system (34-inch
90 textile lighting/display). We started by imparting specific electronic functionalities onto a single fibre
91 (shape/aspect ratio in Method, Supplementary Information 1), then wove individual fibres into a
92 textile (Fig 1a). The fabrication method for the smart textile is compatible with standard textile
93 technologies and equipment (manual or machine loom) so that an unlimited size of textile can be
94 fabricated (Fig. 1b). We note that the symmetric weaving pattern was used to build the smart textile,
95 except that the asymmetrical weaving pattern was used to protect an active area of F-devices,
96 especially F-photodetector and F-biosensor module, and to align the F-LED (Supplementary Fig. 1).
97 Then, the novel smart textile system was achieved by the six woven F-devices programmed along
98 with a full-colour 34-inch display (F-LED) (Fig. 1c). All fibre devices were connected using highly
99 conductive fibres (developed in-house, Ag-coated polyamide (Ag-PA), Supplementary Fig. 2, Table 1
100 and 2) that allow signal transfer from an F-device to an assigned controller that relays the information
101 to the F-LED display (output). The nature of the textile enables the entire system to be folded, rolled,
102 bent for wall-mountable curtain lighting/display (less than 5 mm-thick, Fig. 1d). We first interpret the
103 performance of F-devices comprising the smart textile system along with mechanical and electrical
104 stability followed by explaining the operation principle of the system.

105 **Fibre devices characteristics**

106 All F-devices fitted to weaving/interconnection process are uniquely designed and optimised for our
107 textile system. Each F-device involved in the smart textile system shows core-shell structure or is
108 fabricated onto a single fibre. As a pivotal output device (F-LED), lighting and display apparatus, the
109 textile lighting/display consists of $84 \times 76 \times \text{RGB LEDs}$ (1.91×10^4 subpixels) mounted onto copper
110 fibres and woven with cotton fibres line by line asymmetrically (ratio 1:3 for F-LED versus cotton
111 thread) to avoid distortion of visualising images (Supplementary Fig. 3). We also developed the F-
112 LED with $120 \times 65 \times \text{RGB LEDs}$ (2.34×10^4 subpixels) to enhance the resolution. It is noteworthy that
113 no higher resolution of textile display with fibre LEDs has yet been demonstrated. Further reduction
114 of the inter-LED distance led to the interference between neighbouring pixels resulting in inhibiting
115 single-pixel control. At low operation voltage ($< 3 \text{ V}$), the luminance exceeded 10^4 cd/m^2 for RGB
116 colours while maintaining their colour purity and brightness under shape change (Supplementary Fig.
117 3e, Movie 1, 2).

118 F-RF antenna, a square spiral antenna designed to receive the electromagnetic field at the distances
119 from the RF source (frequency of 13.56 MHz) (Fig. 2a) was fabricated by embroidery method using
120 Ag-PA conductive fibres (20 filaments/thread, Supplementary Fig. 4) for a mode switch ('display
121 mode' to 'monitoring mode'). The antenna properties and design rules are summarised in
122 Supplementary Fig. 5a,b and Table 3. The inductance of antenna is proportional to the number of
123 turns. In contrast, the width of an embroidered straight line is inversely proportional to the
124 inductance²⁸⁻³⁰. Total inductance of embroidered antenna was $L_{\text{measure}} = 2.64 \mu\text{H}$ (Supplementary
125 Fig. 5c, the deviation is 6.04%, compared to the simulated inductance, L_{Wheeler}). The impedance of
126 F-RF was $95.3 + j220 \Omega$ at 13.56 MHz (Supplementary Fig. 5d).

127 F-photodetectors consist of aluminum (Al)/zinc oxide (ZnO)-graphene photoactive layer/epoxy
128 encapsulation layer structure on polyethylene naphthalate (PEN) fibres. Eight-channel F-
129 photodetectors connected in parallel in the textile woven with the asymmetrical pattern were tested
130 via UV irradiation (0.5 mW) (Fig. 2b). The results show that a detector generates a maximum of ~
131 100 times increase in photocurrent at $V_{\text{bias}} = 10 \text{ V}$ and exhibits average rise and decay times of 3 sec
132 and 1 sec, respectively (Supplementary Fig. 6). Compared to the state-of-the-art flexible ZnO-based

133 photodetectors, our F-photodetector that was integrated into the textile under harsh mechanical stress
134 relatively exhibits low operating voltage and fast rise (decay) time along with comparable on/off ratio
135 (Supplementary Fig. 6).

136 Network of F-touch sensors is achieved using Ag-PA conductive fibres that exhibit a change in
137 resistance (converted to the output voltage signal as the function of touch duration from 1s to 30 s)
138 when touched (Fig. 2c, Supplementary Fig. 7). Those conducting fibres were woven into the textile in
139 the weft (horizontal) and warp (vertical) directions with spacings of 2 and 3 cm, respectively. The
140 weft conducting fibres are encapsulated by a polyolefin tube (yellow in Supplementary Fig. 7) while
141 vertical fibres are left exposed to air. This method allows complex, simultaneous, and multi-touch-
142 read functions that are comparable to a touchpad. An electrical readout circuit acquires the change in
143 resistance ($\Delta R(R_{touch} - R_{release})/R_{release} \times 100 \geq 2\%$) as fast as 1 Hz. F-touch sensor shows the
144 response times of 18 ms from noise to the maximum resistance change (Supplementary Fig. 7).
145 Signal-to-noise ratio ($SNR = 20\log_{10}(V_{signal}/V_{noise})$) exhibits higher than 70 dB, which is
146 sufficient for identifying active/inactive status.

147 Two core-shell copper/copper oxide (Cu/Cu₂O) fibres twisted together were used to realise F-
148 temperature sensors woven in the textile system, which show that the resistance continuously
149 decreases as a function of increasing temperature from 5 °C up to 70 °C when placed on a hot plate
150 (Fig. 2d). Cu₂O is a well-known negative temperature coefficient material (Supplementary Fig. 8)^{31,32}.
151 The characteristics of F-temperature sensor fit well with the Steinhart-Hart model³³, as shown in Fig.
152 2d. In order to evaluate the sensitivity of F-temperature sensor, temperature coefficient of resistance
153 of 1.44±0.36 %/K at the reference temperature of 25 °C was extracted (Supplementary Fig. 9a,b),
154 which shows an estimated resolution of approximately 0.1 °C (Supplementary Fig. 9c) similar to
155 state-of-the-art F-temperature sensors^{2,34}. The most sensitive temperature range for the F-temperature
156 sensor is found to be between 5 °C to 70 °C that is applicable for real-life indoor/outdoor conditions.
157 The origin of thermal conduction can be found by the extracted thermal activation energy of Cu₂O
158 that is 0.266 eV, which is consistent with copper vacancy level (V_{Cu}) from valence band maximum
159 (Supplementary Fig. 9d)³¹.

160 F-biosensor module based on an amplifier in a common-source configuration consists of F-transistor
161 and a resistor along with an electrocardiogram (ECG) pad (Fig. 2e, Supplementary Fig. 10a). The
162 woven transistor was achieved by the asymmetrical weaving pattern along with laser soldering with
163 Ag glue within 1 sec (details of laser soldering and alignment in Supplementary Fig. 10b–d and
164 material property in Table 4). Tailored fibre transistors with indium gallium zinc oxide (IGZO) as the
165 channel exhibit threshold voltage (V_{TH}) = 0.9 V, on/off ratio = 10^7 , saturation mobility (μ_{sat}) = 8
166 $\text{cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ that shows one-year stability in ambient environment (Supplementary Fig. 11a,b).
167 Theoretical amplification gain (defined as $A_v = g_m R_D$)³⁵ can be obtained from transconductance and
168 resistance of a load resistor (R_D). To maximize empirical voltage gain ($A_v = \partial V_{out}/\partial V_{in}$), a resistor
169 of 70 M Ω was connected as a bias load to ensure that the heartbeat signal (typically less than 1 mV)
170 reaches a voltage gain of ~ 28 V/V at its peak (Fig. 2e, Supplementary Fig. 11c). As the device
171 operated at the bias current of 131 nA in the saturation regime, the peak power consumption was
172 found to be 350 nW indicating low power consumption as a peripheral module in the smart textile
173 system (Supplementary Fig. 11d).

174 Double twisted fibre supercapacitors (F-energy storage) consisting of gel-electrolyte (polyvinyl
175 alcohol (PVA)/ H_3PO_4) between carbon fibre (CF) bundles have also been integrated into smart textile
176 system as a trigger switch between power supply and textile lighting/display instead of the main
177 power source as the power consumption of output lighting/display LED is measured to be a maximum
178 of 35 W (Fig. 2f, Supplementary Fig. 12). Five serially connected fibre supercapacitors show the total
179 output voltage of 5 V (discharging curve during operation of textile lighting/display, display-off
180 below 2.6 ± 0.1 V, Fig. 2f). To increase the capacitance of fibre supercapacitor, conductive fibre (Ag-
181 PA) was incorporated into CF bundle resulting in a 3-fold increase in total capacitance
182 (Supplementary Fig. 12). Fibre supercapacitors exhibit an average capacitance of 5.47 ± 0.78 mF (CF
183 only) and 17.5 ± 0.6 mF (CF with Ag-PA) at a scan rate of 100 mV/s. Among fibre supercapacitors
184 (electrical double-layer capacitors) reported to date, our supercapacitor with conductive fibre shows
185 high specific energy and power output.

186 **Mechanical and electrical stability of fibre devices**

187 Strong emphasis on mechanical and electrical stabilities has been given to fibre devices^{14,36}. To
188 evaluate the mechanical stability and electrical reliability of each F-device, cyclic bending under 10
189 mm radius or stretching tests have been performed. F-LED, as the output device, maintains initial
190 electrical characteristics over a year (Supplementary Fig. 13) and shows unnoticeable current density
191 change under 1000 bending cycles ($\Delta V_{J=100 \text{ mA/cm}^2} = 0.2 \text{ V}$, $\Delta J_{1000 \text{ cycle}, r=10 \text{ mm}} = \pm 5 \text{ mA/cm}^2$)
192 owing to highly flexible copper fibre (Fig. 3a).

193 In the case of conductive fibre, we note that it does not alter its conductivity (approximately 2.32×10^6
194 S/m, Fig. 3b) against 10 mm bending condition so that the harsh stretching test was performed
195 (Supplementary Fig. 14). A conductive fibre that is crucial for transferring electronic charges from F-
196 devices to controllers, as well as the essential material for F-RF antenna, F-touch sensor, F-energy
197 storage, and device interconnection, was located on step-motored elongation stage. Continuous cycling
198 strain up to 20% showed constant current of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ A}$ under $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ V}$. It was found that uni-axial
199 strain of more than 35% resulted in a breakdown of conductive fibre that is significantly overqualified
200 for mechanical bending or rolling condition of the entire smart textile (Supplementary Fig. 15)

201 F-photodetector, fixed bending radius 10 mm, was tested under cyclic mechanical manipulation (Fig.
202 3c). At the bias voltage of 10 V, off-current and on-current were continuously maintaining near 9.3
203 nA (relative standard deviation: 5.82%) and 278 nA (relative standard deviation: 8.62%), respectively
204 that confirmed the electrical stability during 1000 bending cycles. It is clear that ‘on-off’ current still
205 lies in the distinctive range that is substantial enough to categorise photonic input identification.

206 F-touch sensor is based on the resistive mode responding to finger contact. Weariness of conductive
207 surface layer would result in a non-resistance change at a contact position. After operational touch
208 intensity (on-status) was set to $\Delta R/R_{max} = 0.5$ (Fig. 3d), 1000 touch attempts (3000 touch results in
209 Supplementary Fig. 7h) were performed leading to an average of 0.78 ($\Delta R_{avg}/R_{max}$, relative
210 standard deviation: 4.86%) that is indicative all the touch signals displayed higher than ‘on-status’, in
211 turn, the conductive layer (Ag) was not affected during repeating touches.

212 F-RF antenna is made of conductive fibres, which shows slight resistance change during 1000
213 bending cycle (Fig. 3e). As comparable with single conductive fibre characteristics in Fig. 3b, the
214 electrical current along with spiral square antenna was maintained that indicated the unchanged
215 antenna property in terms of output voltage, output power, rectified signal against the distance
216 (Supplementary Fig. 16).

217 F-temperature sensor sustained its original conductivity under bending conditions of 10 mm radius
218 (Fig. 3f) because the active layer mechanically protected by the encapsulation layer. However, owing
219 to the oxide material nature, even F-temperature sensor was encapsulated by epoxy, the resistance was
220 increased over one-year period (*e.g.* at $T = 40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $R_{\text{original}} = 47\text{ k}\Omega$, $R_{1\text{-year}} = 263\text{ k}\Omega$, Supplementary
221 Fig. 9), because of further oxygen diffusion into F-temperature sensor originated from water
222 (moisture) vapour transmission rate of epoxy in ambient³⁷. We note that the increasing current trend
223 as a function of temperature was maintained for segmenting temperature levels, which can be
224 compensated by adjusting programming code variables.

225 When fibre transistor of F-biosensor module is subjected to bending, the electrical characteristics are
226 influenced due to channel and dielectric leakage current under mechanical stress. To identify the
227 working condition limit, 1000 cycle bending with a radius of 10 mm (Fig. 3g, lower bending
228 conditions in Supplementary Fig. 11e) was applied resulting in unnoticeable transfer characteristics
229 change ($\Delta V_{TH} = -0.92\text{ V}$, $\text{on/off} = 10^7$) that is suitable for F-biosensor module. The n-type channel
230 material (IGZO) with encapsulation layer (parlylene-C) does not show a notable change in its mobility
231 ($\Delta\mu_{sat} < 0.45\text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$) and threshold voltage ($\Delta V_{TH} < 0.5\text{ V}$) over a year (Supplementary Fig. 11a,b)
232 that reflects material stability is achieved.

233 Bundle of CFs with or without conductive fibres in F-energy storage device is damage-free from 1000
234 bending cycles (radius of 10 mm) confirming mechanical manipulation of smart textile is viable (Fig.
235 3h). Besides, the electrolyte (PVA- H_3PO_4) layer does not show any noticeable capacitance
236 degradation over a year ($\Delta C = 0.26\text{ mF}$) or during 1000 cyclic charge-discharge tests (over 0.95),
237 which further reveals electrochemical stability of F-energy storage by ideal capacitance retention
238 (Supplementary Fig. 12).

239 Further investigation of mechanical reliability of F-device-embedded textile is performed by abrasion
240 test for three functional textiles which are subjected to be touched, pressed or possible fatigue over a
241 time without protective layer (Supplementary Fig. 17); (i) LED-embedded cotton textile, (ii)
242 conductive fibre embroidered cotton textile, and (iii) conductive fibre embroidered polyester textile.
243 The standard disc-type Martindale-abrasion test revealed that RGB LED and conductive fibres
244 maintain their original properties (luminance of 1000 ± 10 cd/m² and conductivity of $2.32\times 10^6\pm 0.5$
245 S/m) after 1000 cycles of abrasion test under 1 kg load which is suitable for decorative use in non-
246 wearable applications (ISO 12947-1).

247 **Operation principle of smart textile display system**

248 As a proof-of-concept of smart textile lighting/display system, we connected six devices including F-
249 RF antenna, F-photodetector, F-temperature, F-touch sensor, F-biosensor module to textile display,
250 and F-energy to display power switch and utilised the integrated textile system as a smart home
251 appliance. The working principle of the integrated smart textile system is summarised in Fig. 4a;
252 incoming signals from individual F-devices (by electromagnetic, photonic, physical, environmental,
253 and biological) require several steps of signal process and categorisation, then being visualised on the
254 textile display. Several controllers are connected to F-devices with a specific circuitry to operate the
255 smart textile display system (Photo in Fig. 4a).

256 The textile display in the smart textile system can work in both ‘display mode’ (grey-level-controlled
257 moving pictures and lighting as shown in Supplementary Movie 1 and 2) and ‘monitoring mode’ (still
258 images presenting the information from each F-device, Supplementary Movie 3 to 7, examples of RF
259 signal strength, photodetection, touch, temperature, and biosignal) using F-energy storage as a switch
260 between main power supply and textile display (Supplementary Movie 8).

261 F-RF, F-photodetector, F-temperature, and F-biosensor module activated by radio frequency waves
262 (13.56 MHz), UV light (365 nm), ambient temperature, and biosignal, respectively, as contactless
263 devices inform electromagnetic field contents, weather elements, and cardiac activity.

264 As the RF-transmitter is brought near an embroidered F-RF square spiral antenna, the response, *e.g.* a
265 colour-bar chart (classified at 2.5, 2, 1.5, 1, 0.7, 0.4, 0.2 V, Fig. 4b, Supplementary Fig. 16 and Movie
266 3), appear on the textile display depending on a signal reception range (0 to 6 cm). At the maximum
267 detection range (6 cm), the textile display turns from 'display mode' to 'monitoring mode' as rectified
268 input signal triggers mode change, whereas the withdrawal of RF-transmitter away from the antenna
269 instantly draw the mode back to 'display mode' which indicates the removal of RF signal.

270 The motivation for F-photodetector and F-temperature integration in the smart textile system stems
271 from environmental monitoring. UV detection function of F-photodetector is verified by that the
272 smart textile system displays the university logo upon UV illumination on light-sensitive layer of
273 ZnO-Graphene (Fig. 4c, Supplementary Fig. 18 and Movie 4). When the system is installed on the
274 window, *e.g.* smart curtain, F-photodetector facing outward reads UV intensity. Dependence on UV
275 protection range from 15% up to 100% (under AM1.5G) shows F-photodetector current ranges from
276 5×10^{-8} A to 3×10^{-7} A that allows determination of window coverage (Supplementary Fig. 19, roll-
277 up/down smart textile curtain). F-temperature sensor was introduced to monitor indoor/outdoor
278 environment temperature. It was used to obtain the resistance values from which a real-time
279 temperature was calculated and displayed (Fig. 4d, Supplementary Fig. 20). To monitor temperature
280 response, grasping F-temperature sensor by fingers was performed to mimic fast environmental
281 temperature change that revealed spontaneous temperature response (Supplementary Movie 5).

282 To read the heartbeat from one of the authors (Fig. 4e and Supplementary Movie 6), the output
283 voltage from F-biosensor module was used. F-biosensor module is able to amplify 0.5 mV from the
284 body signal to 12.5 mV (empirical voltage gain $A_v = \partial V_{out} / \partial V_{in} = 25 \pm 2$) and the real-time
285 heartbeat is plotted on the textile display without the use of an external amplifier (Supplementary Fig.
286 21, bpm = 80, 120 before/after running, respectively).

287 F-touch device is activated by physical stimuli (contact mode). F-touch sensors were designed to
288 operate each fibre device as well as show a set of pre-coded instructions on the textile display when
289 touched (Fig. 4f, Supplementary Movie 7). The circuitry was made by interconnecting Ag-PA fibres
290 with touch sensors array (Supplementary Fig. 22). To implement practical real-life applications, thirty

291 execution terms for smart gadgets and internet of things (IoT) were demonstrated to every sensor
292 element (Supplementary Fig. 23 and Table 5).

293 F-energy storage was connected between textile display and the main power supply (35 W, $V_{\text{output}} = 5$
294 V) to turn on the textile display by applying a voltage to the switch (Fig. 2g, the configuration in
295 Supplementary Fig. 12a, Supplementary Movie 8). After the operation for 300 sec resulting in voltage
296 drop to 2.6 ± 0.1 V, the textile display turns off.

297 Thermal stability of textile display in the smart textile system was tested as a safety measure and
298 showed that the temperature variation of less than 2 °C (from 24.7 to 26.2 °C) was observed over a
299 continuous operation for 6 hours (Supplementary Fig. 24). The standard water resistance property of
300 all fibre devices in our textile system have been investigated under IPX7 condition (1 m deep, 30 min)
301 and revealed that all F-devices exhibited unnoticeable performance change (Supplementary Movie 9,
302 Supplementary Fig. 25).

303 **Conclusion**

304 We have successfully merged textile engineering and fibre-based electronics in order to integrate a
305 fully functional versatile smart textile system. A large (46-inch) smart textile system exhibits high
306 luminance RGBW lighting/display coupled with six functional fibre devices capable of real-time
307 electromagnetic, physical, signal monitoring with freedom of form factor. Our systematic integration
308 of multifunctional F-device into textile platform will be a cornerstone and give a guideline for not
309 only electronic engineers but also traditional textile engineers in the emerging smart textile field to
310 overcome dimensional and form factor limitations.

311 **Methods**

312 **Weaving Process.** To weave the smart textile system with six F-devices and F-LED (width: 60 cm),
313 the number of weft-warp threads counts more than a thousand. Precise design of entire textile system
314 and position of electronic F-devices should be considered prior to weaving process. Mechanical and
315 performance degradation during the weaving to F-RF, F-touch sensor, F-temperature sensor, and F-
316 energy storage is negligible owing to conductive fibre-based device architecture and a protective
317 coating layer. In contrast, F-photodetector and F-biosensor module are weak to mechanical abrasion
318 during the weaving. To increase openness of active area of those mechanically sensitive F-devices, we
319 adopted an asymmetrical weaving pattern that those unwanted fibres detour to the peripheral position
320 of F-devices. An asymmetrical weaving pattern is also required to prevent electrical short-circuit
321 between conductive fibres which are in contact with electrodes of F-devices (Supplementary Fig. 1).
322 Considering these critical pattern-related parameters, the number of conductive threads in warp
323 direction should be determined before the weaving process to isolate the functional device without
324 electrical interference. At the same time, the number of non-conductive threads in both warp/weft
325 directions should also be considered before the weaving process as the density of threads influences
326 the maximum bending radius owing to interlacing tension.

327

328 **Fabrication of conductive fibre.** A feeding reel has 1-kilometer-long pre-treated polyamide (PA)
329 fibre (Supplementary Fig. 2). Pre-treatment, either surface roughening or seed-layer (platinum, Pt)
330 deposition, was done for promoting silver nanoparticle adhesion and nucleation/growth. The raw fibre
331 feeding speed (Supplementary Table 1) and minimum/maximum of deposition speed, temperature,
332 volume of electrolyte, current density, Ag layer thickness during the electroplating step were adjusted
333 depending on Ag thickness and relative conductivity (Supplementary Table 2). After electroplating of
334 conductive layer, two steps of washing were done to remove residual electrolyte. Drying of Ag-PA
335 fibres was done in a vacuum box before collecting fibres on retrieving reel.

336

337 **Fabrication of fibre LED.** Full-colour RGB F-LED that allows the dynamic visual monitoring of
338 input stimuli detected by F-devices were made by modified conventional LED pick-place method^{38,39}.

339 The textile display in the smart textile system consists of display size of 34-inch and a screen
340 resolution of 84×76 and 120×65 pixels. Designed pixel-to-pixel pitches on the F-LED were 7 mm and
341 5 mm, respectively. To achieve a better resolution textile display, we re-designed a flexible copper
342 fibre (width 4 mm) with patterned electrodes by chemical copper etching. Solder paste was applied to
343 each LED mounting location. After placing LEDs aligned with soldering paste on a copper fibre, hot-
344 dry reflowing (< 250 °C, solidifying solders) was performed. To achieve single-pixel operation,
345 overlapping of reflowed-solder paste was inhibited by leaving the least amount of solder paste
346 (Supplementary Fig. 3a).

347 Interconnection between following F-LED was done by conductive fibre (Supplementary Fig.
348 3b). Two power lines (\pm) with one data line were connected at the one end of each F-LED. Power and
349 data lines were connected by zig-zag route to define the positions of LEDs. To minimise image
350 distortion, the horizontal position of F-LED was adjusted during the weaving process (Supplementary
351 Fig. 3c,d). A controller has limited data accessibility up to 700 pixels, which indicates we added one
352 controller every eight LED fibres, leading to 10 controllers that were required to operate a 34-inch
353 textile display (photo of all controllers in Fig. 4a). In J - V - L curves of RGB LED, the luminance
354 consistently increased with increasing operating voltage, transcending the industry-standard
355 luminance (Samsung, LG, and Signify) for lighting (> 10,000 cd/m²) and large display (> 1,000
356 cd/m²) purposes at low operation voltage below 3 V (Supplementary Fig. 3e).

357

358 **Fabrication and design rules of F-RF antenna.** We investigated a textile RF antenna with a square
359 spiral shape that has the advantage of operating over a wide range of frequencies by length adjustment
360 and increasing inductance by adding multiple turns of the pattern. The dimension of the F-RF antenna
361 is first determined by width (W) and length (L) of 2-dimensional shape (2D). Our antenna was
362 designed to be a square spiral type (W=L). Ag-PA conductive fibres were used to form a square spiral
363 antenna by embroidery method on cotton fabric (Area_{cotton} = 400 cm², Supplementary Fig. 4). To
364 achieve higher conductivity, twisted threads (20 filaments per thread) were fed to the embroidering
365 machine by transferring a custom-design pattern. To convert RF signal (AC) to DC voltage, a rectifier

366 bridge was made by connecting 4 diodes (RS1G E3 400 V SMD diode) where two-terminals from the
 367 antenna connections were marked V1, V2 as incoming RF signal (Supplementary Fig. 4).

368 Calculated antenna properties and design rules of the square spiral antenna are summarized in
 369 Supplementary Fig. 5 and Table 3. Based on a modified Wheeler formula and expression on current
 370 sheet approximation^{28,29}, the inductance of antenna (shape, length (L), width (W), line width (w), line
 371 spacing (s), and connectors) was calculated to maximize the signal reception as shown in
 372 Supplementary Fig. 5. When a squared antenna design is considered, based on the modified Wheeler
 373 formula, the inductance of the antenna is given by (parameters are summarized in Supplementary
 374 Table 1)^{28,29,40,41};

$$375 \quad L_{wheeler} \approx K_1 \cdot \mu_0 \cdot N^2 \cdot \frac{D_{avg}}{1+K_2 \cdot \delta}$$

376 The overall inductance of an antenna is determined by parameters including; the average diameter of
 377 the antenna, $D_{avg} = 0.5(D_{IN} + D_{OUT})$, K_1 and K_2 are Wheeler parameter indexes (inductance
 378 reduction factors), μ_0 is the permeability of free space ($4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m), N denotes the number of turns,
 379 and δ is filling ratio ($(D_{OUT} - D_{IN})/D_{OUT} + D_{IN}$). Another simple and accurate expression including
 380 the antenna's layout parameters is also employed based on approximation of one side of a spiral
 381 antenna as a current sheet approximation with uniform current distribution (CSA model).

$$382 \quad L_{CSA} \approx \frac{1}{2} \cdot \mu_0 \cdot N^2 \cdot D_{avg} \cdot c_1 \cdot \left(\ln \left(\frac{c_2}{\delta} \right) + \frac{c_3}{\delta} + c_4 \delta^2 \right)$$

383 where, c_1 , c_2 , c_3 , and c_4 are dimensional correction parameters (Supplementary Table 3). When both
 384 equations were used for the calculation, their difference in the total inductance does not heavily rely
 385 on the calculation models (Supplementary Fig. 5a). In contrast, the number of turns, the width of
 386 conductive lines, and outer length (or width) (D_{OUT}) of antenna have more influence over other
 387 parameters (Supplementary Fig. 5b,c). Discrepancies of values obtained from measurements and
 388 calculations ($discrepancy (\%) = 100 \times (L_{meas} - L_{wheeler})/L_{wheeler}$) stem from embroidered
 389 nature of the F-RF antenna that omits void-free, two-dimensional planar conductive lines on an
 390 insulating substance (cotton or polymeric substrate).

391

392 **Fabrication of F-photodetector.** ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized according to our previous
393 report with minor changes^{42,43}. Briefly, zinc acetate dehydrate was dissolved in methanol (4.5 mmol)
394 followed by heating up to 60 °C. Potassium hydroxide was dissolved in methanol (7 mmol) and added
395 to zinc acetate solution. After cooling down to room temperature, ZnO nanoparticles were collected
396 by centrifuging at 8,000 rpm for 10 min. The graphene flakes were prepared by the liquid-phase
397 exfoliation method, according to our previous report⁴⁴. Briefly, 10 mg/ml graphite flakes in N-
398 Methyl-2-Pyrrolidone were ultrasonicated for 9 hours followed by washing in ethanol three times. To
399 inhibit aggregation of exfoliated graphene flakes, 0.1 ml ammonium solution to 100 ml graphene
400 solution was added followed by washing/re-dispersion in ethanol three times. The mixed solution of
401 ZnO and graphene with the addition of ethylene glycol and isopropanol was prepared for drop-
402 coating. Before coating of ZnO/graphene film, aluminum electrodes on PEN fibre were deposited by
403 thermal evaporation with a shadow mask. The drop-coated ZnO/graphene film was post-annealed at
404 150 °C for 10 min to remove residual solvent (Supplementary Fig. 6). To protect the device during the
405 weaving process, optical adhesive (Norland 65) was deposited only on top of photoactive layer.

406

407 **Fabrication of F-touch sensor.** The first step of weaving process is to align warp (vertical direction)
408 threads on a loom. As our F-touch sensor features 5 × 6 (horizontal × vertical, total 30 sensor points)
409 arrangement, the distance of conductive fibres (Ag-PA) was determined to be 8-threads counts in
410 vertical direction (3 cm, Supplementary Fig. 7). The distance of horizontal conductive fibres was
411 maintained for 2 cm to avoid touch interference.

412

413 **Fabrication of F-temperature sensor.** Copper fibres ($\Phi = 500 \mu\text{m}$) were annealed in air to oxidize
414 surface, resulting in the formation of Cu_2O layer ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$, Supplementary Fig. 8a) on the surface of
415 copper fibre (core/shell structure). Combustion was initiated by using a butane (C_4H_{10}) torch in the air
416 for 1 min with a consequence of surface oxidation ($T_{\text{annealing}} < 287 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). X-ray diffraction (XRD)
417 pattern confirmed Cu_2O phase (Supplementary Fig. 8b,c). Two core-shell type Cu/ Cu_2O fibres
418 (Supplementary Fig. 8d) were twisted to meet the requirement for temperature sensor while
419 measuring resistance until the resistance value lied between 10 k Ω to 1 M Ω . Overlapped part of

420 twisted Cu/Cu₂O (length: 5 mm) was encapsulated by epoxy to prevent further environmental effects
421 (moisture, oxygen, etc.). Copper fibres (around 60 cm) left over after the twisted Cu/Cu₂O were
422 woven into the textile system, then utilised to connect into a signal analyser by conductive fibres.

423

424 **Fabrication of F-biosensor module and detail interconnection strategy.** A fibre transistor was
425 made based on our previous report with slight modification^{45,46}. Briefly, gate electrode, Molybdenum
426 (Mo) was deposited by a sputter in pure Ar atmosphere on PEN (125 µm thick) substrate. The
427 thickness of Mo was measured to be 60 nm. Dielectric layer of 160 nm-thick, seven-layer stacks
428 composed of alternating SiO₂-Ta₂O₅ (1 nm/min, 3.4 nm/min deposition rate, respectively)⁴⁷ is
429 sputtered in Ar/O₂ to obtain high capacitance 96 nF/cm² with mechanical flexibility. A 40-nm thick
430 indium gallium zinc oxide (IGZO) semiconductor was deposited by sputtering (2:1:1 atomic ratio of
431 In:Ga:Zn). As a top contact configuration, 60-nm thick Mo was sputtered for source and drain
432 electrodes. The semiconductor layer was patterned by lift-off process while the gate electrode was
433 patterned by reactive ion etching by sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) (Supplementary Fig. 10a). To protect
434 entire transistor area, parylene-C layer (1.2 µm) was deposited by chemical vapour deposition
435 followed by etching all electrode (gate, drain, and source) parts for conductive fibre connection. A
436 flexible substrate was cut into fibre shape (width = 3 mm) by a laser cutting tool. The interconnection
437 from fibre transistor to an external power source is shown in Supplementary Fig. 10b. Before the
438 weaving process, conductive fibres were aligned where gate, drain, and source electrodes will be
439 located. When one transistor is well-aligned, conductive fibres were attached to Mo electrodes by
440 conductive glue (chemical composition in Supplementary Table 4). The area of dispensed conductive
441 glue was carefully controlled to be smaller than Mo electrodes (minimum: 1 mm × 3 mm).

442 After conductive glue is left on a target area, laser soldering (XTec, Hacker Automation) was done to
443 instantly solidify conductive glue. The laser spot diameter size and focal length were 400 µm and 10
444 cm, respectively. During the laser illumination, a real-time camera equipped with a pyrometer
445 checked the temperature of conductive glue (Supplementary Fig. 10c). Measured temperature as a
446 function of irradiation time was optimised for preventing peeling-off of Mo electrode (Supplementary
447 Fig. 10d). The temperature range over 200 °C damaged both Mo electrode and underneath PEN

448 substrate leading to unfavourable catastrophe. The temperature during the laser annealing was kept at
449 150 ± 10 °C for a second.

450

451 **F-energy storage device fabrication.** F-supercapacitor were prepared by coating solid-gel electrolyte
452 (polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)- H_3PO_4) on carbon fibres reported elsewhere⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰. Briefly, PVA was
453 dissolved in DI water at 140 °C followed by drop-wise addition of H_3PO_4 into PVA solution. This gel
454 electrolyte was continuously stirred for 2 hours before coating it on carbon fibres. The electrolyte was
455 coated on straightened carbon fibre (60 cm-long) by **manual** brushing (3 times), then dried at room
456 temperature. Two carbon-electrolyte fibres were twisted together to form an electrical double layer.
457 To prevent short-circuit or breakdown of capacitive layer, twisted fibres were coated by electrolyte
458 solution twice. To increase the total capacitance of F-energy storage device, we added conductive
459 fibre into carbon fibres bundle, which exhibits a 3-fold capacitance increase (Supplementary Fig. 12).
460 Other coating and twisting remained the same as the procedure in this section.

461

462

463 **Data Availability**

464 The data support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon
465 reasonable request.

466

467 **Code Availability**

468 The codes used for the smart textile system in this study are available at
469 https://github.com/jiajiey/smart_textile_system.

470

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477 **Author contributions:** H. W. C. and J. M. K. conceived the project. H. W. C., G. A, L. G. O., R. M.,
478 M. C., J. M. K. supervised the project. The interconnection, programming/coding, and weaving of
479 fibre devices were carried out by H. W. C., D. S., J. Y. and S. L., C. L. F., R. B., R. I., and P. B.,
480 developed fibre-metal oxide thin film transistor. U. E., S. S., S. N., and A. C. developed planar/woven
481 RF antenna. K. U. developed highly conducting fibres. H. L. developed a fibre photodetector and
482 optimised it for weaving process. S. J., S. D. H., S. Y. B., S. Z., W. H., Y. S., X. F., T. H. L., M. C.,
483 Y. C. performed device morphology analysis, light-emitting diode characterization, antenna property
484 measurement, and touch sensor reliability test. P. J., F. M. M., V. G. C. carried out weaving of
485 upgradable textile units. M. S. developed conductive glue for interconnection. D. J., A. M., R. M., J.
486 G., N. D., A. N., K. C., S. C., S. M., C. K., K. S. developed weaving pattern, interconnection method,
487 large scale device fabrication, and whole system integration. M. L. assisted in the design of
488 lighting/display unit integration. Y. L., S. C., J. I. S. developed fibre energy storage device. H. W. C.,
489 D. S., S. L., J. Y., M. C., and J. M. K. wrote the paper. All authors discussed the results and
490 commented on the manuscript.

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492

493

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617

618 **Fig. 1 | The fabrication protocol and mechanical stability of smart textile system integrated with**

619 **six F-devices and lighting/display apparatus (F-LED).** Technology convergence between textile

620 engineering and electronic science for smart textile display system fabrication; **a, Schematics of F-**

621 **devices and corresponding fabricated F-devices.** **b,** Textile technology (weaving). **c,** Smart textile

622 system. **d,** Mechanical stability of smart textile display system under folding, bending, rolling

623 conditions and side view of the wall-mountable system.

624

625

626 **Fig. 2 | Characteristic of six F-devices. a**, F-RF antenna, Output voltage generated from F-RF

627 antenna with a suppressing resistor demonstrates distance-dependent signal classification. **b**, $I_{\text{light}}/I_{\text{dark}}$

628 as a function of time of F-photodetector under various input voltage under UV on and off. **c**, Touch

629 output signal as a function of touch duration. **d**, Negative resistance changes as a function of

630 temperature of Cu_2O F-temperature sensor. **e**, Amplified (gain ~ 25) heartbeat by F-biosensor module.

631 **f**, Serially connected fibre supercapacitors as power switch of textile lighting/display (on/off).

632

633

634 **Fig. 3 | Mechanical and electrical stability of F-devices, 1000 cyclic bending test with 10 mm**

635 **radius. a, F-LED showing no current density change. b, Stable current of conductive fibre. c, F-**

636 **photodetector showing clear on/off classification. d, Cyclic touch attempts for evaluating surface**

637 **weariness of F-touch sensor. e, Stable resistance value of RF-antenna (Ag-PA conductive fibre). f, F-**

638 **temperature sensor showing stable classification of measured temperature range as a function of**

639 **electrical current. g, Unnoticeable transfer characteristics change of fibre transistor used for F-**

640 **biosensor module. h, Mechanical damage-free from the bending for fibre supercapacitor.**

641

642

643 **Fig. 4 | Design of smart textile display system from material to system level. a**, List of F-devices

644 integrated into the smart textile system, materials, device architecture, auxiliary parts, signal
645 processing/coding, and F-LED visualising. Applications displaying on textile system: Real-time

646 operation photos of **b**, Six-signal strengths digitized depending on the distance between F-RF antenna

647 and transmitter. **c**, Programmed image initiated by UV irradiation on F-photodetector. **d**, Real-time

648 temperature monitoring by F-temperature sensor grasped by fingers. **e**, Electrocardiography signal

649 measured by F-biosensor module. **f**, One of 30 IoT functions operated by F-touch sensor. **g**, F-energy

650 as a power supply to the switch of textile display.